

FOREST4EU partner: GIS

OG: eGozd

OG's country: Slovenia

Type of Innovation: Service

A system for Quality assessment of Forestry Contractors

Introduction

The forestry services market is dynamic. Skilled forestry contractors are needed to meet the increased demand for wood and to maintain a competitive edge in forestry. There is often limited knowledge about how well they fulfil demands about resource efficiency, social responsibility and environmental protection. The problem is particularly apparent when there is an increased demand for services in the event of large-scale disturbances (ice and wind storms, bark beetle attacks, etc.), when individual forest owners do not have information about service providers and their quality and reliability. Clients of services, especially small forest owners who need services less often and have no experience with forest management, make their decisions mainly based on intuition and personal acquaintances. That is why an online system was developed for the assessment of forestry contractors following sustainability principles. A system for assessing the quality of forestry contractors in Slovenia "MojGozdar" consists of three levels: (1) Formal suitability of forestry contractors based on available data sources on business entities; (2) Expert assessment of suitability of forestry contractors; (3) Customer rating on service quality. In addition to the requirements for professional competences and legislative obligations, the system proposes a number of additional requirements such as corporate social responsibility, participation in the local community and greater environmental responsibility. The forestry contractor and the certification body sign a cooperation agreement to obtain the expert assessment. The expert assessment is performed by an evaluator authorized by a certification body. A web service has been introduced with the purpose of serving as a communication tool between professional evaluators and forestry contractors, as well as providing a new possibility for forest owners to get direct contact with forestry contractors. The system enables its users to exert influence on the assessment of forestry contractors by assessing the quality of their services. Private forests greatly benefit from customer feedback information on the service quality. MojGozdar offers users support in searching for skilled forestry contractors: cutting with a chainsaw, skidding, silviculture works, fully mechanized harvesting, production of wood chips (chopper), forest construction, transport of round wood and wood chips, purchase of wood on the truck road.

Lessons learned

The MojGozdar online system is an important connecting link between Slovenian forest owners and other forestry service seekers on the one hand, and forestry contractors on the other. The reaction to MojGozdar is positive both from the part of the contractors and users. The user provides a wide range of options, from searching for contractors and establishing contacts with them, to digital management of key

documentation related to the implementation of forestry works. Such tools are also very interesting from a statistical point of view. When the majority of contractors in a country are included in such a system, it will also give a good overall statistic about the number and size of contractor companies, as well about the kind of services that they provide.

The online information system MojGozdar represents the beginning of the establishment of modern information and communication flows and as such raises the level of digitization in the field of efficient and economically sustainable forest management and directly affects the increase in productivity and added value in the entire forest and wood production chain.

Figure 1: Overview of digital platform.

For further information contact

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The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.mojgozdar.si/>

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